

Tuning the Morphology of Block Copolymer-Based pH-triggered Nanoplatfoms as Driven by Changes in Molecular Weight and Protocol of Manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

The ability to tune size and morphology of self-assemblies is particularly relevant in the development of delivery systems. By tailoring such structural parameters, one can provide larger cargo spaces or produce nanocarriers that can be loaded by hydrophilic and hydrophobic molecules starting ideally from the same polymer building unit. We herein demonstrate that the morphology of block copolymer-based pH-triggered nanoplatfoms produced from poly(2-methyl-2-oxazoline)_m-*b*-poly[2-(diisopropylamino)-ethyl methacrylate]_n (PMeOx_m-*b*-PDPA_n) is remarkably influenced by the overall molecular weight of the block copolymer, and by the selected method used to produce the self-assemblies. Polymeric vesicles were produced by nanoprecipitation using a block copolymer of relatively low molecular weight ($M_n \sim 10 \text{ kg.mol}^{-1}$). Very exciting though, despite the high hydrophobic weight ratio ($w_{\text{PDPA}} > 0.70$), this method conducted to the formation of core-shell nanoparticles when block copolymers of higher molecular weight were used, thus suggesting that the fast (few seconds) self-assembly procedure is controlled by kinetics rather than thermodynamics. We further demonstrated the formation of vesicular structures using longer chains *via* the solvent-switch approach when the “switching” to the bad solvent is performed in a time scale of a few hours (approximately 3 hs). We accordingly demonstrate that using fairly simple methods one can easily tailor the morphology of such block copolymer self-assemblies, thereby producing a variety of structurally different pH-triggered nanoplatfoms *via* a kinetic or thermodynamically-controlled process. This is certainly attractive towards the development of nanotechnology-based cargo delivery systems.

Keywords: block copolymers; micelles; polymersomes; morphology control; nanoprecipitation; solvent-switch; pH-responsiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The self-assembly is certainly the core of many biological transformations (for instance, the membrane of living cells is the result of phospholipid self-assembly) and it can be also frequently observed in our daily life (for instance, the soap bubbles are the result of surfactant self-assembly). The final morphology of self-assembled amphiphilic block copolymers follows essentially the same principles reported for small molecules, and it can be controlled by selecting an appropriate hydrophilic-to-hydrophobic volume ratio. This is thermodynamically governed by the packing parameter p given by:

$$p = \frac{v}{a l} \quad (1)$$

with v and l being respectively the volume and length of the hydrophobic block, and a the area at the hydrophobe-hydrophile interface. Commonly, spherical micelles is produced when $p \leq 1/3$, cylindrical micelles are formed at $1/3 < p \leq 1/2$ and vesicles (commonly referred to as polymersomes) when $1/2 < p \leq 1$. [1,2].

Indeed, due to such a versatility and the higher colloidal stability compared to self-assemblies from small molecules, [3] those produced from block copolymers are considered in a wide array of applications including nanoreactors for biocatalysis, [4] nanofabrication, [5] cell mimicking [6] and many biomedical strategies. [1] Taking into account particularly the potential applications in the biomedical field, polymer-based supramolecular nanostructures designed to respond to environmental stimuli (pH, temperature, redox potential, light, magnetic field, presence of specific enzymes, to name a few) are of higher interest. [7–9] Along these lines, poly[2-(diisopropylamino) ethyl methacrylate] (PDPA) is pH-switchable with $pK_a \sim 6.8$. [10] Due to the high metabolic rate of cancer cells and the resulting local accumulation of H^+ ions, tumor sites are characterized by low local pH (ranging from 6.0 to 7.0 depending on the tumor

site and aggressiveness) compared to the normal pH value found in healthy tissues (pH ~7.4).[11] Therefore, PDPA-based assemblies are potentially relevant to be used in tumor targeting and tumor detection methods.[12–14] Furthermore, an important concern in this particular field is the exhaustive use of PEGylated formulations (also included in food and cosmetic products) which enables their recognition by specific antibodies.[15] This feature notably attenuates the therapeutic effect of PEG-based formulations and therefore, the searching for PEG alternatives is highly relevant.[16] In this framework, a variety of possible substitutes have been investigated including, for instance, poly[*N*-(2-hydroxypropyl) methacrylamide] (PHPMA)[17], poly(glycerols)[18] and poly(2-oxazoline)s (POx).[19] Truly, despite the literature reports concerning diblock copolymers containing POx, block copolymers combining poly(2-methyl-2-oxazoline) (PMeOx) and the highly valuable pH-switchable block PDPA has been only reported by us to the best of our knowledge.[20] Therefore, this investigation constitutes a step forward to better understand the feasibility to tune size and morphology of pH-responsive nanoplatfoms for biomedical applications produced from PMeOx_m-*b*-PDPA_n block copolymers.

Truly, polymeric micelles and polymersomes have great potential as cargo agents, and the ability to tune size and morphology is valuable since these structural parameters influence for instance the endocytosis pathway and tissue extravasation.[21] Moreover, cellular uptake is size-dependent with maximum rates suggested at radius of approximately 25 nm.[22,23] Taking into account the protocols to produce polymeric self-assemblies, thin-film rehydration, solvent-switch and nanoprecipitation are straightforward approaches.[6,24,25] In the thin-film rehydration, the block copolymer is dissolved in an organic solvent commonly using round-bottom glass vials. The solvent is further evaporated producing a thin-film which is then hydrated upon the addition of an aqueous solution. The method usually requires at least a couple

of days to obtain the self-assembled structures in a process that is governed by thermodynamics. To overcome the time-consuming drawback, other strategies have been proposed such as the solvent-switch technique. In such a method, the block copolymer is also solubilized in an organic solvent and afterwards, water (a poor solvent for the hydrophobic block) is slowly added and therefore, the quality of the solvent changes in a timescale usually of a few hours. The progressive increase in the interfacial tension between the hydrophobic blocks and water triggers the self-assembly in a process that is also controlled by thermodynamics. Concerning the nanoprecipitation approach, a previously prepared polymer organic solution is fast injected into a water phase (in the time scale of a few seconds). The organic phase (which must be water miscible) diffuses towards the water phase provoking the spontaneous self-assembly of the block copolymer chains. The main difference compared to the solvent-switch method is the speed of common and selective solvent mixing.

Indeed, depending on the manufacturing protocol, the non-ergodic nature of block copolymers permits the production of kinetically trapped morphologies out of the thermodynamic equilibrium. Although the copolymer composition regularly drives the final morphology, this can be bypassed *via* rapid solvent mixing (in the time scale of a few seconds). Actually, by using the nanoprecipitation approach, the solvent quality is lost very fast which may not favor the arrangement of the polymer chains in the most stable equilibrium structure as governed by the packing parameter. Since the kinetics of self-assembly is notably accelerated and the block copolymer chains may not have sufficient mobility during the process to reach the most stable thermodynamic morphology, the assemblies may then be trapped in a metastable structure. This behavior has been previously admitted to take place with block copolymers comprising a glassy hydrophobic segments such as poly(methyl methacrylate) and polystyrene whose glass transition temperature (T_g) is notably higher than the ambient temperature.[26,27]

Nevertheless, kinetically frozen systems, stable over months in aqueous media, were also evidenced for assemblies containing hydrophobic blocks with notably low glass transition temperature such as poly(*n*-butyl acrylate) (PnBA) whose T_g value is around -55 °C.[28,29] Accordingly, the dynamics of self-assembly seem not be driven by the T_g of the hydrophobic block, but it is the hydrophobic block-solvent interfacial tension which might govern the phenomenon.

Taking into account all the above-mentioned considerations, we herein investigated the methods of preparation in the production of self-assemblies from a library of amphiphilic PMeO x_m -*b*-PDPA n diblock copolymers. The nanoprecipitation and the solvent-switch protocols were selected to rationalize the relationship between copolymer chain length, hydrophilic-to-hydrophobic weight ratio, method of self-assembly, size and morphology in a reasonable timescale which may be useful towards scaling-up purposes. The resources of dynamic and static light scattering (SDLS), small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and cryo-TEM were used to demonstrate the control over size and particularly, morphology of the pH-responsive nanoplateforms. We demonstrated that these features can be tuned by properly selecting the molecular weight of the building units and a slower or a faster self-assembly procedure. The findings are certainly highly valuable since different morphologies and sizes can be reached by using even the same block copolymer chains by changing the protocol of preparation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals

The block copolymers poly(2-methyl-2-oxazoline) $_m$ -*b*-poly[2-(diisopropylamino)-ethyl methacrylate] $_n$ were synthesized as previously described using a stepwise combination of

cationic ring-opening (CROP) and reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) polymerization techniques.[20] Based on such strategy, a variety of chains with distinct length (molecular weight) and hydrophobic-to-hydrophilic weight ratio were produced. The Figure 1 shows the schematic representation of the synthetic procedure and the molecular structure of the produced block copolymers.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the synthetic approach used in the preparation of PMeOx_m -mCTA macro chain transfer agent (A) and PMeOx_m -*b*-PDPA_n block copolymers (B).

The solvents methanol (anhydrous, 99.8%) and tetrahydrofuran (anhydrous, $\geq 99.9\%$), Dulbecco's phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and the dialysis bag Spectra-Por[®] Float-A-Lyzer[®] G2 with MWCO 3.5-5 kDa were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The water used in the sample preparation was pretreated with a Milli-Q[®] Plus System (Millipore Corporation).

Preparation of the Polymer Colloids

Nanoprecipitation: Five-mg of the polymer samples were dissolved in 2 mL of THF/methanol (40/60 v/v). The organic polymer solutions (THF/MeOH 40/60 v/v, 2.0 mL,

$c_{\text{polymer}} = 2.5 \text{ mg.mL}^{-1}$) were fast (1 mL.min^{-1}) injected into PBS buffer pH 7.4 (5.0 mL). The resulting samples were transferred to a dialyses bag and dialyzed for 48 hs against PBS to remove the solvent.

Solvent-Switch: Five-mg of the polymer samples were dissolved in 1 mL of THF/methanol (60/40 v/v). Subsequently, PBS solution was slowly added dropwise into the polymer organic solution (first hour: 25 μL every 3 mins up to a final volume of 500 μL , then 50 μL every 3 mins up to a final volume of 2000 μL , and finally 500 μL at once). The solvent was further removed by transferring the samples to a dialysis bag and dialyzed for at least 48 hs against PBS.

Methods of Characterization

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS): DLS measurements were performed using a ALV/CGS-3 compact goniometer system consisting of a 22 mW HeNe laser ($\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$), an ALV 7004 digital correlator and a pair of APD-based single photon detectors. The samples were loaded into 10 mm diameter glass cells and maintained at $25 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The data were collected using the ALV Correlator Control software (the acquisition time was 60 s in all cases). The intensity autocorrelation functions (based on 3 averaged independent runs) were acquired at scattering angle $\theta = 90^\circ$ and they were analyzed using the algorithm CONTIN incorporated in the ALV correlator control software, thus resulting in distributions of relaxation times - $A(\tau)$ which were further converted into distributions of R_H by using the Stokes-Einstein equation:

$$R_H = \frac{k_B T}{6\pi\eta D} \quad (2)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, η is the viscosity of the solvent and D is the diffusion coefficient ($D = \tau^{-1}q^{-2}$) being τ the mean relaxation time and q the scattering vector (q):

$$q = \frac{4 \pi n}{\lambda} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where n the refractive index of the solvent.

Static Light Scattering (SLS): In the SLS mode, the absolute light scattering was monitored in the angular range from 30° to 150° (based on 3 measurements with $\pm 5\%$ maximum error between runs). The weight-average molecular weight ($M_{w(NPs)}$) and to the radius of gyration (R_G) of the nanoparticles were determined by using the partial Zimm plot:

$$\frac{Kc}{R_\theta} = \left(\frac{1}{M_{w(NPs)}} \right) \left[1 + \frac{R_G^2}{3} q^2 \right] \quad (4)$$

where K is the optical constant which includes the square of the refractive index increment (dn/dc), R_θ is the excess normalized scattered intensity (toluene was applied as standard) and c is the polymer concentration given in mg.mL^{-1} . The values of number of aggregation (N_{agg}) were determined as $N_{\text{agg}} = M_{w(NPs)}/M_{w(\text{polymer})}$. The values of dn/dc for the $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_n$ block copolymers in aqueous solution were computed taking into account the additive rule[30] with $(dn/dc)_{\text{PMeOx}} = 0.18 \text{ mL.g}^{-1}$ [31] and $(dn/dc)_{\text{PDPA}} = 0.14 \text{ mL.g}^{-1}$ as based on determined values of dn/dc for PDPA-based self-assemblies.[32]

Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS): The ELS measurements were conducted using a Zetasizer NanoZS apparatus (Malvern Instruments). The surface charge of the assemblies was determined by measuring the electrophoretic mobility (U_E) and further converting the value to zeta potential (ζ) using the Henry's equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{3 \eta U_E}{2 \varepsilon f(ka)} \quad (5)$$

where ε is the dielectric constant of the medium. The parameter $f(ka)$ is the Henry's function which has been calculated using the Smoluchowski approximation with $f(ka) = 1.5$. The data were acquired at 25 ± 1 °C and they are reported based on 3 averaged measurements with 20 sub-runs each.

Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS): The SAXS profiles were recorded by using a pinhole camera (MolMet, Rigaku, Japan, modified by SAXSLAB/Xenocs) attached to a microfocused X-ray beam generator (Rigaku MicroMax 003) operating at 50 kV and 0.6 mA (30 W). The samples were sealed into borosilicate capillaries (~ 2 mm diameter) and the scattering intensities were recorded using a Pilatus 300K detector with exposure time of 480 min (8 hs). The scattering profiles could be fitted using the form factor of spherical bilayered vesicles and a summary of this model is briefly described in the following section. The fitting procedures and other analysis were performed using the SASfit software package developed by J. Kohlbrecher and available free of charge.

Cryo-Transmission Electron Microscopy (Cryo-TEM): The cryo-TEM observations were performed at the Brazilian Nanotechnology National Laboratory (LNNano). The images

were acquired on a Talos Arctica G2 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) high-resolution TEM at accelerating voltage of 200 kV equipped with a Ceta 16M 4K CMOS imaging camera (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and the TEM Imaging & Analysis version 4.21 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) software. The images were recorded in the low dose imaging mode to reduce electron-beam radiation damage. The samples were prepared at 22 °C and 100 % relative humidity in a controlled environment vitrification system (FEI Vitrobot) thus avoiding water evaporation from the specimen. Three- μ L of the samples were loaded into 01895 - Lacey Carbon, 300 mesh, copper electron microscopy grids (Electron Microscopy Science). The excess of the liquid samples was removed by blotting with filtering paper grade 595 (Ted Pella). The grids were then immediately plunged into liquid ethane. The TEM grids were previously submitted to a glow discharge system (glow time 25 s, glow charge -15 mA), the specimens were stored in liquid nitrogen and then transferred under controlled conditions into the autoloader cassette. The autoloader was transferred to the microscopic column and the temperature was kept at -182 °C during these procedures.

RESULTS

Synthesis of the Block Copolymers

The syntheses of macro chain transfer agents (PMeO_x_m-mCTA) carrying the RAFT CTA 4-cyano-4-(phenylcarbonothioylthio)pentanoic acid were performed *via* cationic ring-opening polymerization of MeO_x in a microwave reactor at 130 °C, and the reaction mixture was terminated by adding CTA and TEA under stirring overnight at 50 °C in an oil bath. The PMeO_x_m-mCTA were then used in the copolymerization procedures conducted with the pH-sensitive DPA monomer. The Table 1 provides the structural parameters of the polymer chains which were detailed characterized by proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) and size exclusion chromatography (SEC).

Table 1. Molecular characteristics of the PMeO_x_m-*b*-PDPA_n block copolymer chains as determined by SEC and ¹H NMR.

Entry	$M_n(\text{SEC})$ ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) ^a	D^a	$M_n, ^1\text{H NMR}$ ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) ^b	$M_n(\text{PDPA})$ ($\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) ^b	w_{PMeOx^c}
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₃₅	7 770	1.20	10 200	7 700	0.24
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₅₅	11 870	1.14	14 400	11 900	0.17
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₀	25 770	1.18	22 700	19 980	0.12
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	17 560	1.17	30 800	26 200	0.15
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	28 250	1.26	52 000	45 300	0.13

^aDetermined by SEC in chloroform-triethylamine-isopropanol (94/4/2 vol%). ^bDetermined by

¹H NMR in D₂O/DCI. ^cWeight fraction of the hydrophilic block based on ¹H NMR data.

The subscripts refer to the degrees of polymerization of each block as determined by ^1H NMR. The diblock copolymers were synthesized with higher amounts of the hydrophobic segment, respectively lower amounts of PMeOx. The molecular weight of the amphiphilic molecules (M_n determined by ^1H NMR) ranges from $10.2 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ to $52.0 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ with a relatively narrow polydispersity ($D \leq 1.26$).

Self-Assembly of the Block Copolymers

Influence of the Molecular Weight on the Morphological Behavior

We firstly have investigated the influence of the molecular weight on the final morphology of $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_n$ self-assemblies by using the protocol of nanoprecipitation. This is herein demonstrated taking into account the PMeOx_{26} -based diblock copolymers. The influence of molecular weight is indeed clearly evidenced in the reported experimental data. Figure 2 portrays the autocorrelation functions monitored at $\theta = 90^\circ$ and respective intensity-weighted distributions of sizes revealed by the CONTIN analysis for self-assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation from $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{35}$, $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{55}$ and $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{110}$ according to the legend.

The averaged values of hydrodynamic radius (R_H) obtained as the output of the CONTIN analysis are provided in Table 2. The size, which is at least to some extent linked to morphological aspects, are notably different and dependent on the overall molecular weight of the polymer chains. Indeed, noticeably bigger size was monitored by dynamic light scattering for the shortest polymer chains of the investigated series ($\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{35}$). The large self-assemblies are characterized by hollow spheres (polymersomes) as discussed hereafter. On the other hand, longer chains ($\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{55}$ and $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{110}$) conducted to notably smaller nanoparticles with the size presumably not physically compatible with polymeric

vesicles, although they contain even higher amounts of the hydrophobic segment (PDPA) as given in Table 1. The manufacturing of notably larger particles produced from $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{35}$ is robustly evidenced in the cryo-TEM images reported in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Autocorrelation functions $C(q,t)$ monitored at $\theta = 90^\circ$ (top) and respective intensity-weighted distributions of sizes (bottom) revealed by the CONTIN analysis for diblock copolymer self-assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation using $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{35}$ (black), $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{55}$ (red) and $\text{PMeOx}_{26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{110}$ (blue) according to the legend ($c_{\text{polymer}} = 1.0 \text{ mg.mL}^{-1}$).

Table 2. Structural features of the manufactured block copolymer self-assemblies as determined by scattering measurements and imaging (the self-assemblies were prepared by nanoprecipitation).

Entry	R_H (nm)	$R_{\text{stretched}}$ (nm)	$R_{\text{entangled}}$ (nm)	N_{agg}	$N_{\text{agg-stretched}}$	$N_{\text{agg-entangled}}$	ζ (mV)	Morphology
PMeOx ₂₆ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₃₅	89.1	21.9	6.8	36900	716	21	-4	Vesicles
PMeOx ₂₆ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₅₅	19.3	29.3	8.2	438	1770	34	-4	Micelles
PMeOx ₂₆ - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₀	25.9	49.5	11.2	595	7070	65	-3	Micelles

If one correlates experimental and theoretical approaches, and initially considers the presence of core-shell assemblies with spherical geometry, their radius (R) can be estimated by calculating the contour length of each block as:

$$R = R_{\text{core(PDPA)}} + L_{\text{shell(PMeOx)}} = a_{\text{PDPA}} N_{\text{PDPA}}^b + a_{\text{PMeOx}} N_{\text{PMeOx}}^b \quad (6)$$

being $R_{\text{core(PDPA)}}$ and $L_{\text{shell(PMeOx)}}$ respectively the radius of the core and thickness of the shell, N_{PDPA} and N_{PMeOx} the degrees of polymerization of PDPA and PMeOx, and a_{PDPA} and a_{PMeOx} the lengths of a PDPA (0.367 nm)[33] and PMeOx (0.35 nm)[34] repeating unit. The dimensions scale with $b = 1$ in one boundary (fully stretched chains) whereas $b = 0.5$ for Gaussian coils. The value of $b = 2/3$ is expected for entangled chains. The values for maximum ($R_{\text{stretched}}$) dimension ($b = 1$) and for a more realistic ($R_{\text{entangled}}$) conformation ($b = 2/3$) are also given in Table 2. Clearly, the experimental average dimension of the PMeOx₂₆-*b*-PDPA₃₅ self-assemblies ($R_H = 89$ nm) exceeds remarkably the value of $R_{\text{stretched}}$ ($R_{\text{max}} = 21.9$ nm) highlighting

accordingly that the size is not compatible with the formation of core-shell structures. This morphology is therefore assigned as polymersomes (hollow spheres).

Figure 3. Cryo-TEM images of PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₃₅ (A), PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₅₅ (B) and PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ (C) diblock copolymer self-assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation ($c_{\text{polymer}} = 1.0 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$).

The morphological observations through cryo-TEM evidences homogenous and spherical structures. The polymeric vesicles (polymersomes) as assigned for the assemblies seen in Figure 3A may have different appearances in cryo-TEM. The characteristic ring-shape similar to liposomes can be evidenced, but also images with higher contrast within the lumen are usually observed such as in the current case. The higher contrast in the central part is surprising at a glance since the inner cavity is supposed to be filled with the same solution of the surroundings. Nevertheless, this is a typical observation when the vesicles are larger than the thickness of the vitrified water layer.[35,36] Yet, it is the comparison between the theoretical and experimental dimensions which indeed more robustly suggest the presence of hollow spheres.

The notably smaller dimensions monitored for PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₅₅ and PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ are unlikely to be linked to the formation of hollow spheres (polymeric vesicles) and therefore, core-shell structures were presumably produced. The hydrodynamic dimensions are found to be in between the theoretical values of $R_{\text{stretched}}$ and $R_{\text{entangled}}$, thus underscoring that the chains adopt a relatively extended conformation (uncoiled chains), although notably far from the fully extended configuration. Furthermore, the self-assemblies produced from PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ are clearly bigger than the ones produced from PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₅₅. Since the length of the hydrophilic segment (PMeO_{x26}) is the same, this is presumably related to a larger dimension of the hydrophobic PDPA core as the length increases. Additionally, the behavior may be also connected to a higher number of aggregation (N_{agg}). Indeed, although the

radius of gyration of the assemblies are too small to be reliably determined by static light scattering ($R_G < \lambda_{\text{source}}/20$, $\lambda_{\text{source}} = 632.8$ nm) since the light scattered is essentially independent of the scattering angle, the weight average molecular weight and respective number of aggregation could be determined (Table 2). The value is indeed higher for PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ (595) compared to PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₅₅ (438) nevertheless, a remarkably larger value has been determined for PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₃₅ (36 900) underscoring once again the presence of different morphologies in solution.

The presence of polymeric vesicles (polymersomes) produced from PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₃₅ is also suggested by the estimated values of aggregation number (N_{agg}) as compared to the experimental ones. The theoretical numbers were calculated assuming a PDPA core without the presence of solvent as:

$$N_{\text{agg}} = \frac{N_A d}{M_{w(\text{PDPA})}} \left(\frac{4\pi R_{\text{core}}^3}{3} \right) \quad (7)$$

where $M_{w(\text{PDPA})}$ is the weight-average molecular weight of PDPA, N_A is the Avogadro number, d is the density of PDPA (~ 1 g.cm⁻³) and R_{core} was estimated as $R_{\text{core}} = r_{\text{PDPA}} = aN^b$. The maximum value of N_{agg} taking into account fully stretched chains ($b = 1$) would be 716 for PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₃₅ and therefore, the experimental value is notably higher once again suggesting the presence of polymeric vesicles. The experimental values for PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₅₅ and PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ possibly suggest, in agreement with previously discussed data, that the polymer chains adopt an extended conformation within the core-shell assemblies which is most likely due to the solution pH lying close to $\text{pK}_{a(\text{PDPA})}$ (~ 6.8). Although the working pH (7.4) is higher than $\text{pK}_{a(\text{PDPA})}$, according to the profile of the molar ratio of deprotonated species *vs.* pH,[20] approximately 20% of the amino groups in the PDPA chains

are still protonated at $\text{pH} = 7.4$, thus resulting in the presence of relatively swollen hydrophobic segments.

The presence of different morphologies as a function of the molecular weight is surprising to some extent considering the higher amounts of the hydrophobic segment (PDPA) respectively, lower amounts of the hydrophilic section - PMeOx (Table 1). Therefore, the formation of core-shell assemblies using diblock copolymer composed by higher amounts of the hydrophobic segment is interesting since this feature was expected to conduct to the formation of polymeric vesicles in thermodynamic equilibrium which have not been detected in the manufacturing of $\text{PMeO}_{x26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{55}$ and $\text{PMeO}_{x26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{110}$ assemblies by nanoprecipitation. Accordingly, the core-shell structures are presumably kinetically trapped. The nanoprecipitation protocol enables a faster solvent diffusion compared to the kinetics of self-assembly thus conducting to frozen morphologies although this is not the most stable equilibrium structure (taking into account the thermodynamic point of view respectively, the packing parameter). Nevertheless, even using such fast technique, vesicles could be produced from $\text{PMeO}_{x26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{35}$ possibly due to its shorter dimension. These results underscore that, although the morphology is frequently driven by the hydrophobic-to-hydrophilic weight ratio, which in such cases would solely lead to the formation of polymeric vesicles since $w_{\text{PDPA}} > 0.75$, the DLS and cryo-TEM data robustly confirm the development of different morphologies produced by nanoprecipitation which seems to be driven by the overall molecular weight of the polymer chains. Accordingly, the formation of the most stable equilibrium structure for such block copolymer chains can be bypassed by the rapid solvent mixing which then does not favor the arrangement of the polymer chains nevertheless, this is observed only for the longer block copolymer chains whereas for the shorter ones, polymersomes could be produced even by

nanoprecipitation. Whenever produced, the kinetically-trapped core-shell nanoparticles remain stable over several months (data not shown for brevity).

Influence of the Manufacturing Protocol on the Morphological Behavior

We have further investigated the influence of the manufacturing protocol on the morphological behavior of $\text{PMeOx}_m\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_n$ spherical nanoparticles. In such way, the self-assemblies were produced by the nanoprecipitation and solvent-switch approaches using the same polymer chains. The influence of the manufacturing protocol is clearly evidenced in the data reported in Figures 4 and 5, and in the Tables 3 and 4.

Figure 4. Intensity-weighted distributions of sizes revealed by the CONTIN analysis for diblock copolymer self-assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation (N) or solvent-switch (SS) using PMeOx₂₆-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀, PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ and PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ according to the legends ($c_{\text{polymer}} = 1.0 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). The autocorrelation functions $C(q,t)$ were monitored at $\theta = 90^\circ$.

Figure 5. Cryo-TEM images of self-assemblies produced from PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ by solvent-switch (A) and nanoprecipitation (B), from PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ by solvent-switch (C) and nanoprecipitation (D) and from PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ by solvent-switch (E) and nanoprecipitation (F) with $c_{\text{polymer}} = 1.0 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$.

Table 3. Structural features of the manufactured block copolymer self-assemblies as determined by DLS, ELS and cryo-TEM (nanoprecipitation - N; solvent-switch - SS).

Entry	Method	R_{H}	$R_{\text{stretched}}$	$R_{\text{entangled}}$	ζ	Morphology
		(nm)	(nm)	(nm)	(mV)	
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₀	N	25.9	49.5	11.2	-3	Micelles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	N	18.0	59.3	13.0	-3	Micelles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	N	27.1	94.9	17.2	-4	Micelles
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₀	SS	55.8	49.5	11.2	-6	Vesicles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	SS	43.1	59.3	13.0	-4	Vesicles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	SS	41.9	94.9	17.2	-4	Vesicles

Table 4. Structural features of the manufactured block copolymer self-assemblies as determined by SLS (nanoprecipitation - N; solvent-switch - SS).

Entry	Method	R_G (nm)	R_G/R_H	$M_w \times 10^7$ (g·mol ⁻¹)	N_{agg}	$N_{agg-stretched}$	$N_{agg-entangled}$	Morphology
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₀	N	-	-	1.35	595	7070	67	Micelles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	N	-	-	0.95	308	7460	69	Micelles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	N	-	-	2.68	515	25800	129	Micelles
PMeO _{x26} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₀	SS	48.9	0.87	7.02	3090	7070	67	Vesicles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	SS	40.7	0.95	5.80	1880	7460	69	Vesicles
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	SS	41.8	0.99	6.02	1150	25800	129	Vesicles

Figure 4 provides the intensity-weighted distributions of sizes revealed by the CONTIN analysis for diblock copolymer self-assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation (N) or solvent-switch (SS) using PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀, PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ and PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀. One can see that the distribution of sizes is always located at the right-hand side for self-assemblies produced by using the SS approach pointing out accordingly larger structures. The quantitative data are given in Table 3 and they confirm bigger self-assemblies produced using the solvent-switch approach compared to nanoprecipitation, regardless of the polymer chains. The theoretical values of $R_{stretched}$ and $R_{entangled}$ were also added to the experimental values reported in Table 3 for comparison purposes. Initially, one can already notice that R_{max} ($R_{stretched} = 49.5$ nm) is smaller than the average hydrodynamic radius monitored for PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ produced by solvent-switch (55.8 nm) underscoring that the assemblies cannot be assigned as core-shell particles and therefore, polymersomes are supposed to be produced. This behavior already evidences the influence of the manufacturing protocol on the resulting morphology since core-shell nanoparticles were produced from PMeO_{x26}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₀ by nanoprecipitation

as previously discussed ($R_H = 25.9$ nm). Similarly, the self-assemblies produced from samples $\text{PMeO}_{x51}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{113}$ and $\text{PMeO}_{x51}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{210}$ by nanoprecipitation (N) are smaller than those produced by solvent-switch and they were also assigned to core-shell nanoparticles. Indeed, the PMeO_{x51} -based block copolymer chains are longer than the PMeO_{x26} -based counterparts (Table 1) and accordingly, the presence of core-shell assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation once again robustly confirms the influence of the molecular weight on the morphological behavior. Comparable to the previously discussed data, the hydrodynamic dimensions are in between the estimated values of $R_{\text{stretched}}$ and $R_{\text{entangled}}$ thus pointing out that the chains adopt a relatively extended conformation (uncoiled chains) within the core-shell assemblies, although not fully extended. On the other hand, the self-assemblies produced using the same polymer chains but *via* the solvent-switch approach are bigger as clearly evidenced either by DLS or cryo-TEM.

Interestingly, the size of such assemblies is noticeably smaller than the size of the vesicles produced using $\text{PMeO}_{x26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{35}$, and also smaller than the polymersomes produced from $\text{PMeO}_{x26}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{110}$. Although the monitored sizes are still physically compatible with the presence of core-shell nanoparticles ($R_H < R_{\text{stretched}}$), they could only be linked to highly extended chains which is not realistic to some extent. Therefore, we preliminary assign them to the presence of hollow spheres (polymersomes). The estimated values of aggregation number (N_{agg}) as compared to the experimental values also does not rule out the formation of core-shell assemblies taking into account only geometrical constraints. The self-assemblies with $R_G > 30$ nm were also fully characterized by static light scattering and representative data acquired for $\text{PMeO}_{x51}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{210}$ produced by nanoprecipitation (N) and solvent-switch (SS) are provided in Figure 6 along with quantitative data provided in Table 4. The combination of R_G and R_H allows for the determination of the structure sensitive parameter

(ρ -ratio = R_G/R_H) which is occasionally useful to identify different morphologies. The homogeneous hard sphere has a theoretical value of 0.778 and it increases for structures with lower density such as polymeric vesicles ($R_G/R_H^0 \sim 1.0$). The values assigned for polymeric vesicles are all close to ~ 1.0 , hypothetically suggesting the presence of structures with an aqueous lumen rather than compact spheres. Nevertheless, the values of spherical micelles usually fall in the range $R_G/R_H \sim 0.9$ -1.0 due to solvation phenomena and therefore, it is frequently challenging to categorize these two morphologies solely by looking at R_G/R_H data.

Figure 6. Zimm plots acquired for PMeOx₅₁-b-PDPA₂₁₀ self-assemblies produced by nanoprecipitation (N) and solvent-switch (SS).

Nevertheless, the representative data reported in Figure 6 are remarkably different thus strongly suggesting that different self-assemblies were produced. So as to more robustly confirm the morphology of $\text{PMeOx}_{51}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{113}$ and $\text{PMeOx}_{51}\text{-}b\text{-PDPA}_{210}$ self-assemblies produced by solvent-switch, we have further performed small-angle X-ray scattering, and the experimental data are reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7. SAXS profiles (symbols) and respective curve fittings (solid lines) for the block copolymer self-assemblies produced by solvent-switch using PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ (A) and PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ (B) according to the legends. The schematic representation of a bilayered vesicle is given at the bottom along with the structural parameters of SAXS fitting.

The vesicular morphology is suggested for both self-assemblies due to the presence of the typical upward profile at the lower q -range following a q^{-2} power law dependence. Therefore, the characteristic oscillations located at $q \sim 0.2$ - 0.4 nm^{-1} are associated to the vesicle membrane thickness. Indeed, the SAXS patterns of PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ and PMeOx₅₁-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀ self-assemblies produced by solvent switch could only be adjusted by using the bilayered vesicle form factor whereas a core-shell form factor could not properly describe the scattering profiles. The form factor for a bilayered vesicle implemented in the SASfit software is given by:

$$K(q, R_c + t_h + t_t, (\eta_t - n_h) + K(q, R_c + t_t + 2t_h, (\eta_h - n_{sol}))^2 \quad (8)$$

$$I(q) = (K(q, R_c, (\eta_{sol} - n_h) + K(q, R_c + t_h, (\eta_h - n_t) +$$

with:

$$K(q, R, \Delta\eta) = 3V_{sphere} \Delta\eta \frac{\sin QR - QR \cos QR}{(QR)^3} \quad (9)$$

The adjustable parameters of fitting included the radius of the inner compartment consisting of water (R_c), the thickness of the hydrophilic outer section in contact with the solvent (t_h), the thickness of hydrophobic inner segment (t_t) containing the hydrophobic groups and the respective electron densities of the solvent (η_{sol}), outer (η_h) and inner (η_t) sections of the bilayer.

The bilayer vesicle is cartooned at the bottom of Figure 7 with the respective structural

parameters. The electron density of water ($333 \text{ e}^-/\text{nm}^3$) was kept fixed during the fitting procedures and the relevant adjustable parameters are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Structural parameters of the polymeric vesicles as determined by SAXS measurements and further data treatment.

Entry	R_c	t_t	t_h	wall thickness	R_t
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₁₁₃	37.0	7.8	13.4	29.0	66.0
PMeO _{x51} - <i>b</i> -PDPA ₂₁₀	37.4	7.0	17.8	31.8	65.6

wall thickness: $t_h+t_t+t_h$

The fitting procedure using the bilayer form factor evidenced smaller wall thickness for PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ compared to PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀, which is compatible with the shoulder located at a higher q -range and most probably linked to the smaller degree of polymerization of the hydrophobic segment. Truly, notably thick bilayers are suggested by the SAXS data treatment. Taking into account that the membrane thickness can be estimated as:

$$t_t = aN^b \quad (10)$$

and considering the estimated PDPA repeating unit length (0.367 nm),[33] the values are reached considering $b = 0.76$ and $b = 0.73$ respectively for PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₁₁₃ and PMeO_{x51}-*b*-PDPA₂₁₀. Since $b = 1$ would regard fully stretched chains whereas $b = 0.5$ is for Gaussian coils and $b = 0.66$ is expected for entangled polymeric membranes, the values highlight that the

chains adopt a relatively extended conformation as once again attributed to the solution pH lying close to $pK_{a(PDPA)} \sim 6.8$ resulting in relatively swollen hydrophobic blocks.

CONCLUSIONS

Following early investigations regarding the microfluidic-assisted manufacturing of $PMeO_x$ -*b*- $PDPA_m$ self-assemblies,[20] we herein demonstrate the high versatility of such building units to produce compact and hollow spheres with different sizes. Despite high hydrophobic weight ratios ($w_{PDPA} > 0.70$), core-shell nanoparticles could be produced by fast nanoprecipitation, thus *via* a kinetically-controlled process. Although the kinetic effect could be anticipated in forming simpler core-shell structures,[32] we demonstrate that this is a molecular weight-dependent phenomenon that only takes place for relatively long chains ($M_w > 10 \text{ kg.mol}^{-1}$). Nevertheless, polymeric vesicles are developed *via* solvent-switch, therefore when using a lengthy procedure. We accordingly underline that using fairly simple approaches one can easily tailor the morphology and produce cargo spaces able to transport hydrophilic and hydrophobic molecules, even by using the same polymer building unit. This is certainly attractive concerning energy costs and scaling-up purposes. We have further investigated the internal structure of the pH-responsive self-assemblies and demonstrated that they are composed by swollen hydrophobic segments. Investigations underway demonstrate that this feature confers to vesicular structures intrinsic permeability which has been rarely reported for membrane-forming polymers.[37,38] This potentially allows for selective diffusion of molecules which is of due relevance in an array of bio-related applications such as in the construction of artificial biomimetic organelles and protein-loaded nanoreactors.[4] Last but not least, despite other literature reports concerning PDPA-based block copolymer assemblies,[10,33] the combination with PMeOx constitutes another step forward of this

investigation towards finding PEG alternatives as the *in vivo* recognition by specific antibodies[15] is a relevant issue for therapeutic and other medical applications.

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